

A concerted synthesis of hydroxychalcones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans through palladium-catalysed reactions[†]

Mahuya De, Dyuti P. Majumdar and Nitya G. Kundu*

Department of Organic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032, India

Manuscript received 13 September 1999

A convenient palladium-catalysed procedure for the synthesis of *o*-hydroxychalcones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans is described where *o*-iodophenyl acetate was used as a common precursor.

Chalcones, flavonoids and benzo[*b*]furans are important groups of compounds which have found widespread occurrence in nature and they are also of great biological significance. For example, licochalcone A I, isolated from Chinese licorice, is an efficient inhibitor of *Leishmania donovani* and *L. major* promastigotes and amastigotes *in vitro*.

The antileishmanial properties of other chalcones have also been reported². Chalcones have shown anti-inflammatory³, cytotoxic⁴ and anticancer properties⁵. Flavonoids are constituents of fruits and vegetables consumed by human beings. Many naturally occurring and synthetic flavonoids are known to have significant biological activities⁶. The anti-inflammatory, antiviral and antineoplastic activities of flavonoids have been reported⁷⁻⁹. Recently Fu and coworkers¹⁰

have reported the isolation of complex flavanones (2,3-dihydroflavones) from a Malaysian plant *Cryptocarya kurrii* Hook f. (Lauraceae), which showed cytotoxicities against KB cells. Flavonoids have also shown inhibitory activities against a variety of proteases including trypsin and leucineaminopeptidase¹¹, and have been inhibitors¹² of DNA topoisomerase I and II which are involved in the process of DNA replication, transcription and recombination¹³. Several flavonoids isolated from the leaves of *M. morindoides* growing in Zaire, have shown significant anticomplementary activities¹⁴. Very recently, Akama and coworkers¹⁵ have reported that 5,4'-diaminoflavone (II) and some of its congeners showed remarkable antiproliferative activity against the estrogen receptor (ER)-positive and estrogen-responsive human breast cancer cell line MCF-7.

I
Licochalcone A

II

III

IV
Machicendiol

V
Tremetone

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Also, a flavanone derivative (**III**) exhibited strong estrogenic activity¹⁶.

Benzo[*b*]furan derivatives, e.g. machicendiol (**IV**), tremetone (**V**) and others are of considerable interest because of their occurrence in nature and their physiological properties^{14,17}. Due to the occurrence of chalcones, flavones, flavanones and their derivatives in nature and their biological importance, various methods have been developed for the synthesis of these compounds^{6,15,19-25}. Similarly, a number of methods are available for elaborating the benzofuran structure^{17,18,26-32}. Recent trends are however, in the use of palladium-catalysed reactions for carbon-carbon bond formation³³⁻³⁷ and carbon-heteroatom bond formation³⁸.

Thus, a number of methods have been developed for the synthesis of benzo[*b*]furans using palladium-catalysed reactions³⁹. However, methods for the synthesis of flavones and flavanones through palladium-catalysed reactions are limited in number⁴⁰. Kalinin and coworkers^{40b} reported the synthesis of flavones and chromones from the palladium-catalysed reaction of *o*-iodophenols with terminal acetylenes under carbon monoxide at 20 atm pressure (Scheme 1). However, no simple palladium-catalysed procedure for the synthesis of flavanones has been reported yet.

Scheme 1

In continuation of our studies⁴¹ on the development of various heterocyclic structures through palladium-catalysed reaction of terminal alkynes, we report here a very convenient procedure for the synthesis of *o*-hydroxychalcones, fla-

vanones and benzofurans starting from a common precursor, e.g. *o*-iodophenylacetate where palladium-catalysed reactions are used very effectively.

Results and Discussion

When *o*-iodophenyl acetate (**1**) was reacted with acetylenic carbinols (**2-14**) with a terminal acetylenic group in the presence of bis(triphenyl phosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3 mol%) and cuprous iodide (3 mol%) in DMF in the presence of triethylamine (3 eqv.) as a base at room temperature for 24 h, the substituted carbinols (**15-27**) were obtained in excellent yields (72–87%).

This is in contrast to the reactions of *o*-iodophenol with acetylenic carbinols under similar conditions, which led to benzofurans directly^{41a}. The acetoxy alkynols (**15-27**) did not cyclise to the benzofurans under the above conditions. The palladium catalysed alkylation gave the optimum yields by carrying the reaction at room temperature. The increase in temperature did not improve the yields; whereas carrying the reaction at 80° did not yield any products at all (entry 5, Table 1). Similarly, optimum time period for the reaction was found to be 24 h (entries 1 and 2). Cuprous iodide was found to be an important co-catalyst for the alkylation reactions. In its absence there were significant reduction in yields (entries 3 vs 1; 8 vs 7). Similarly use of the phase transfer catalyst system⁴² led to a much lower yield (58%) of the alkylation product (entry 4). We have also used another catalyst system, e.g. $Pd(OAc)_2-PPh_3$ (entry 6) in the presence of K_2CO_3 as a base in DMF but no significant amount of alkynylated product could be isolated.

The acetylenic carbinols used were obtained by the reaction of acetylene gas with aldehyde in the presence of sodium in liquid ammonia⁴³. All the carbinols (**2-14**) had an acetylenic group as terminal moiety and with an aromatic

Scheme 2

Table 1 Synthesis of *o*-hydroxychalcones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans starting from *o*-iodophenylacetate (Schemes 2 and 3)*

Entry	Alkynes	Substituted	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	Flavanones and chromanones	Benzofurans
	2-14 R	alkynols ^a 15-27	chalcones 28-37 Yield(%)	38-49 Yield(%) Yield(%)	50-62 Yield(%)
1	2, C ₆ H ₅	15 (86)	28 (73)	38 (68)	50 (68)
2 ^b	2, C ₆ H ₅	15 (89)	–	–	–
3 ^c	2, C ₆ H ₅	15 (73)	–	–	–
4 ^d	2, C ₆ H ₅	15 (58)	–	–	–
5 ^e	2, C ₆ H ₅	–	–	–	–
6 ^f	2, C ₆ H ₅	–	–	–	–
7 ^a	3, C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	16 (85)	29 (71)	39 (65)	51 (63)
8 ^c	3, C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	16 (62)	–	–	–
9	4, C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>m</i>	17 (88)	30 (70)	40 (63)	52 (58)
10	5, C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>p</i>	18 (83)	31 (70)	41 (61)	53 (60)
11	6, C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>m</i>	19 (80)	32 (68)	42 (62)	54 (52)
12	7, C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>o</i>	20 (78)	33 (67)	43 (60)	55 (62)
13	8, C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₂ -O (3',4')	21 (84)	34 (68)	44 (58)	56 (56)
14	9, C ₆ H ₄ F- <i>p</i>	22 (85)	35 (76)	45 (68)	57 (61)
15	10, C ₆ H ₃ OMe(3'), OCH ₂ Ph(4')	23 (89)	36 (69)	46 (64)	58 (62)
16	11, 2-Thienyl	24 (82)	37 (72)	47 (61)	59 (55)
17	12, Me ₂ CH-	25 (76)	–	48 (59)	60 (69)
18	13, CH ₃ -CH=CH-	26 (73)	–	49 (56)	61 (53)
19	14, H	27 (72)	–	–	62 (58)

^aReactions were usually carried out with (Ph₃P)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), CuI (3 mol%) in DMF with Et₃N (3 equiv) for 24 h at RT

^bReaction was done as under method A but for 48 h at RT

^cReactions were done with (Ph₃P)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), Et₃N (3 equiv) in DMF at RT for 24 h but without any CuI

^dReaction was carried with (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), CuI (3 mol%), K₂CO₃ (2.5 eq), Bu₄NBr (1 eq) in DMF at RT for 24 h

^eReaction was done with (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), CuI (3 mol%), Et₃N (3 eq) in DMF at 80° for 24 h

^fPd(OAc)₂ (2 mol%), PPh₃ (3 mol%), K₂CO₃ (2.5 eq) in DMF at 80° for 16 h was used

*All yields are of chromatographically pure materials and are based on *o*-iodophenylacetate **1**

or aliphatic group (R) on the carbinol carbon. It was observed that where R was an aromatic group, the yields of the alkynylated products were much better (78–88%) compared to the cases (entries 17–19) where R was an aliphatic substituent (yields were 72–76%). However, substituents on the aromatic ring did not make much difference in the yields of the alkynylated products (entries 7 and 9; also 10–12).

The acetoxyalkynols (**15–26**) underwent Maeyer-Schuster rearrangement⁴⁴ in the presence of *p*-TSA in benzene at room temperature to the hydroxychalcones (**28–37**). Rearrangement with concurrent deacetylation took place under the above conditions. The alkynols **25** and **26** under the Maeyer-Schuster conditions at room temperature however, underwent rearrangement and cyclisation yielding the corresponding chromones **48** and **49**, respectively. The hydroxychalcones (**28–37**) could be cyclised with H₃PO₄–HOAc to

the corresponding flavanones (**38–47**). A one-pot synthesis of the flavanones could also be achieved by stirring the alkynols (**15–24**) with *p*-TSA in benzene at room temperature for 24 h followed by refluxing for 6–8 h.

An important feature of the palladium-catalysed reactions of *o*-iodophenyl acetate (**1**) with the acetylenic carbinols (**2–14**) is that the resultant substituted alkynols could not only be converted to the *o*-hydroxychalcones and subsequently to the flavanones, but they could also be converted to the 2-substituted benzo[*b*]furans. Thus, substituted carbinols (**15–27**) on treatment with sodium ethoxide in ethanol or by heating with palladium acetate (5 mol%) in the presence of LiCl (1 eqv.) and K₂CO₃ (2.5 eqv.) in DMF at 80° for 16 h yielded the corresponding benzofurans (**50–62**). The yields of the benzofurans based on **1** were found to be highly satisfactory (56–63%).

Characterisation of products : The substituted alkynols

Scheme 3

(15-27), the *o*-hydroxychalcones (28-37), the flavanones (38-49) and the benzofurans (50-62) were characterised by spectral evidences (IR, UV, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR) and elemental analyses. The IR spectra of the substituted alkynols showed the presence of COCH_3 and $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ at 1760 and 2210 cm^{-1} respectively. This was further supported by ^1H NMR, which showed the ketomethyl group at around $\delta 2.0$. Furthermore, the presence of a singlet at around $\delta 5.50$ – 5.90 confirmed the presence of benzylic proton. In the infrared the chalcones had absorption at 1650 cm^{-1} indicative of the conjugated carbonyl and in the ultraviolet absorption maxima were observed at 330 and 233 nm. The proton NMR doublets at $\delta 7.63$ and $\delta 7.92$ with coupling constant values of 15 Hz indicated the presence of two vinylic hydrogens in the *E*-configuration. The flavanones, obtained after cyclisation, had IR absorption at 1700 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and UV maxima at 321 and 252 nm. In the ^1H NMR the chemical shift positions at $\delta 2.86$ (dd, C-3 H_a), 3.11 (dd, C-3 H_b) and 5.44 (dd, C-2H) confirmed the formation of the flavanones.

In the case of the benzofurans, the appearance of a singlet near around $\delta 6.5$ – 7.1 in the ^1H NMR spectra confirmed the presence of the vinylic proton (3-H) of 2-alkyl or 2-aryl substituted benzofurans, respectively. Also, in their UV spectra all the compounds showed absorption of the type 315, 303 and 225 nm for 2-aryl substituted benzofurans and 283, 275 and 247 nm for 2-alkyl substituted benzofurans.

Conclusion. Thus, we report for the first time a general method for the synthesis of *o*-hydroxychalcones and flavanones starting from *o*-iodophenyl acetate, where palladium-catalysis plays a highly significant role. Since flavanones can be readily converted to flavones, our method thus becomes complementary to the palladium-catalysed procedure for the synthesis of flavones reported by Kalinin and coworkers^{40b}. This method has the advantage that no poisonous carbon monoxide gas need to be used under high pressure. We have also described an alternative method for the synthesis of benzofurans starting from the same precursor, e.g. *o*-iodophenyl acetate. The method can be applied for the synthesis of various naturally occurring and biologically important flavanones, flavones and benzofurans.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on Reichert (285980, Austria) apparatus and are uncorrected. All catalyst and co-catalyst used were commercially available. Solvents and reagents were purified by conventional methods. The petroleum ether used was the fraction boiling at 60 – 80° . Silica gel TLC was performed on 60F–254 precoated sheets. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (60–120 mesh). The acetylenic carbinols were synthesised according to literature procedures.

UV spectra were recorded in spectrophotometric grade ethanol (Baker). IR spectra were taken as KBr plates. ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 solutions were recorded at 60 MHz or 300 MHz. ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 75 MHz.

Substituted alkynols (15-27) by palladium-catalysed cross-coupling reactions of o-iodophenyl acetate with acetylenic carbinols. General procedure: A mixture of *o*-iodophenylacetate (1.91 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2$ (45 mg, 0.064 mmol), CuI (20 mg, 0.105 mmol) in DMF and Et_3N was stirred under N_2 atmosphere at room temperature for 15 min. To it was added 1-phenylprop-2-yn-1-ol (380 mg, 2.87 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. It was then evaporated under reduced pressure, residue treated with water (50 ml) and extracted with CHCl_3 (3 $\times$ 50 ml). The combined extracts was washed with water (3 $\times$ 50 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The resultant residue or: column chromatography (silica gel 60–120 mesh) with 10% CHCl_3 in petroleum ether (b.p. 60 – 80°) afforded the substituted alkynols: 3-(*o*-acetoxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-yn-1-ol (15): Light yellow oil (86%); (Found: C, 76.38; H, 5.37. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 76.67; H, 5.30%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3440, 2220, 1770, 1490, 1450 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 285.4 (log $\epsilon = 3.47$), 277.6 (3.46), 253 (4.31), 243.2 nm (4.26); ^1H NMR (60 MHz, CCl_4) δ 2.00 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.13 (1H, bs, CHOH), 5.53 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.90–7.66 (9H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*p*-methylphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (16): White solid, m.p. 48 – 50° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found: C, 76.75; H, 5.73. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 77.42; H, 5.75%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3360–3280, 2220, 1760, 1480, 1450 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 253 (log $\epsilon = 4.20$), 243.8 nm (4.25); ^1H NMR (60 MHz, CCl_4) δ 2.00 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.23 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.50 (1H, bs, CHOH), 5.46 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.83–7.50 (8H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*m*-methylphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (17): Off white solid (88%) m.p. 66 – 67° (Found: C, 77.07; H, 5.49. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 77.42; H, 5.75%) (pet. ether-benzene); ν_{max} (KBr) 3480–3360, 2220, 1760, 1480, 1440 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 252.6 (log $\epsilon = 4.19$), 241.2 nm (4.20); ^1H NMR (60 MHz, CCl_4) δ 2.04 (3H, s,

COCH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.18 (1H, bs, CHOH), 5.62 (1H, s, CHOH), 7.06–7.52 (8H, m, ArH); 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**18**) : Pale yellow solid (83%); m.p. 120–122° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 72.81; H, 5.47; C₁₈H₁₆O₄ calcd. for : C, 72.96; H, 5.44%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3340–3260, 2210, 1760, 1520, 1450 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 275.4 (log ϵ = 3.52), 252.6 (4.19), 242.8 nm (4.23); ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CCl₄) δ 2.03 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.36 (1H, bs, CHOH), 3.76 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.50 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.73–7.59 (8H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**19**) : Pale yellow solid (80%); m.p. 103–104° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 72.81; H, 5.59. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ calcd. for : C, 72.96; H, 5.44%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3420–3360, 2200, 1760, 1600, 1480, 1440 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 279.4 nm (log ϵ = 3.80), 253.2 (4.12), 240.8 nm (4.27); ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CCl₄) δ 2.03 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.28 (1H, s, CHOH), 3.91 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.73 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.78–7.89 (8H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**20**) : White solid (78%); m.p. 135–136° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 72.73; H, 5.39. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ calcd. for : C, 72.96; H, 5.44%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3420–3360, 2200, 1760, 1580, 1490 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 278 nm (log ϵ = 3.56), 251.9 (4.20), 241.8 nm (4.18); ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CCl₄) δ 2.00 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.86 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.67 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.56–7.78 (8H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**21**) : Yellow solid (84%); m.p. 96–98° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 69.65; H, 4.86. C₁₈H₁₄O₅ calcd. for : C, 69.67; H, 4.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3430–3400, 2210, 1760, 1500, 1490, 1440 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 286 (log ϵ = 3.73), 251.8 (4.21), 242.6 nm (4.26); ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CCl₄) δ 2.02 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.06 (1H, bs, CHOH), 5.55 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.94 (2H, s, O-CH₂-O), 6.77–7.51 (7H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*p*-fluorophenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**22**) : Pale yellow solid (85%); m.p. 116–117° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 71.69; H, 4.53. C₁₇H₁₃O₃F calcd. for : C, 71.82; H, 4.61%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3460–3400, 2200, 1760, 1600, 1500, 1490 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 271.2 (log ϵ = 3.68), 252.8 4.13, 243.2 nm (4.16); ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CCl₄) δ 2.03 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.28 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.52 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.79–7.66 (8H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(*m*-methoxy-*p*-benzyloxyphenyl)-prop-2-yn-1-ol (**23**) : Pale yellow solid (89%); m.p. 163–164° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 74.29; H, 5.47. C₂₅H₂₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 74.61; H, 5.51%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3460–3400, 2200, 1760, 1590, 1500, 1450, 1420 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 337.2 (log ϵ = 3.60), 284.6 (3.90), 241.2 nm (4.26); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.07 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.89 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.16 (2H,

s, CH₂), 5.59 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.84–7.43 (12H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)-1-(2'-thienyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**24**) : Brown liquid (82%) (Found : C, 65.89; H, 4.36. C₁₅H₁₂O₃S calcd. for : C, 66.15; H, 4.44%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3460–3380, 2200, 1760, 1610, 1490, 1400, 1360 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 252.4 (log ϵ = 4.29), 242.6 nm (4.35); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 2.04 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.46 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.85 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.96–7.49 (7H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 20.80, 60.63, 80.91, 93.07, 116.33, 122.29, 125.63, 125.95, 126.12, 126.76, 130.02, 133.19, 144.35, 151.74, 169.23. 1-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)pent-4-methyl-1-yn-3-ol (**25**) : Light yellow liquid (76%) (Found : C, 72.15; H, 6.76. C₁₄H₁₆O₃ calcd. for : C, 72.39; H, 6.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3460–3400, 2960, 2200, 1760, 1490, 1450 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 252 (log ϵ = 4.00), 242.0 nm (4.05); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.87–0.98 (6H, m, 2×CH₃), 1.89–1.91 (1H, m, CHMe₂), 2.23 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.59 (1H, d, CHOH), 6.97–7.40 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 17.86, 18.59, 21.29, 34.94, 68.64, 80.80, 94.51, 117.33, 122.62, 126.32, 129.93, 133.61, 151.95, 169.55. 1-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)hex-4-ene-1-yn-3-ol (**26**) : Light yellow viscous liquid (73%) (Found : C, 72.81; H, 5.99. C₁₄H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 73.02; H, 6.13%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3440–3380, 2910, 2200, 1760, 1640, 1620, 1480, 1440, 1370 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285.2 (log ϵ = 3.80), 253.8 (4.09), 242.6 nm (4.16); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 1.75 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.07 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.03 (1H, d, CHOH), 5.63–5.98 (2H, m, CH=CH), 7.06–7.49 (4H, m, ArH). 3-(*o*-Acetoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-ol (**27**) : Light yellow viscous liquid (72%) (Found : C, 69.17; H, 5.23. C₁₁H₁₀O₃ calcd. for : C, 69.46; H, 5.29%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360–3300, 1760, 1610, 1450, 1360 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 290.6 (log ϵ = 3.98), 252.4 nm (4.10); ¹H NMR (CCl₄, 60 MHz) δ 2.07 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.06 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.63–7.46 (4H, m, ArH).

*Acid-catalysed rearrangement of 3-(*o*-acetoxyaryl)-1-phenylprop-2-yn-1-ol (15-24) to 2-hydroxychalcones (28-37). General procedure :* A mixture of 3-(*o*-acetoxyaryl)-1-phenylprop-2-yn-1-ol (**15-24**; 0.67 mmol) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (15 mg, 0.07 mmol) in benzene (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 24 h (TLC). The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with water (25 ml). It was extracted with CHCl₃ (3×50 ml) and the combined organic layers was washed with water (3×50 ml) and then dried (anh. Na₂SO₄). The residue after removal of solvent was chromatographed (silica gel, 60–120 mesh) and the product was further purified by crystallization. [*E*]-3-Phenyl-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-prop-2-en-1-one (**28**) : Yield 73%, bright yellow solid, m.p.

- 86–87° (pet. ether) (lit.^{42a} 86–87°), (Found : C, 80.71; H, 5.51. C₁₅H₁₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.34; H, 5.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1580, 1490, 1350, 1310 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 316.4 (log ϵ = 4.29), 232 nm (4.05); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.44–7.96 (9H, m, ArH), 12.81 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 118.58, 118.78, 120.08, 128.59, 128.97, 129.58, 130.85, 136.33, 145.41, 163.53, 193.69. [E]-3-(*p*-Methylphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (29) : Yield 71%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 149–150° (pet. ether) (lit.^{42a} 148–149°) (Found : C, 81.31; H, 6.21. C₁₆H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.64; H, 5.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1570, 1490, 1430, 1310 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 330.8 (log ϵ = 4.35), 233.4 nm (4.01); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.41 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H_m), 7.57 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH_o), 7.63 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.95–7.14 (2H, m, ArH), 7.43–7.52 (2H, m, ArH), 12.79 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 21.51, 118.52, 118.73, 118.90, 128.65, 129.54, 129.71, 131.77, 136.21, 141.54, 145.51, 163.48, 193.70. [E]-3-(*m*-Methylphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (30) : Yield 70%, bright yellow solid m.p. 92° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 80.35; H, 5.90. C₁₆H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.64; H, 5.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1670, 1590, 1480, 1430, 1310 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 328.6 (log ϵ = 4.29), 230.4 nm (4.24); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.41 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.95–7.52, 7.54–7.94, 7.94–7.98 (8H, m, ArH), 12.84 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 20.17, 28.76, 117.45, 117.65, 118.68, 124.81, 127.75, 128.04, 128.49, 130.64, 133.35, 135.19, 137.56, 144.53, 162.41, 192.60. [E]-3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (31) : Yield 70%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 88–89° (pet. ether) (lit.^{42a} 88–89°) (Found : C, 75.89; H, 5.81. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1570, 1510, 1450, 1350, 1310 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 366.6 (log ϵ = 4.28), 276.6 (3.66), 242.8 nm (3.99); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.88 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 6.96 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH_m), 7.63 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, ArH_o), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.91 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.92–7.08 (2H, m, ArH), 7.78–7.89 (2H, m, ArH), 12.83 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 55.40, 114.45, 117.49, 118.52, 118.70, 120.04, 127.26, 129.47, 130.50, 136.10, 145.31, 161.95, 163.47, 193.61. [E]-3-(*m*-Methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (32) : Yield 68%, bright orange solid, m.p. 136–138° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 75.93; H, 5.79. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1600, 1560, 1520, 1450, 1340, 1300 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 331.2 (log ϵ = 3.98), 258 nm (3.66); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.83 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 6.90–7.66 (6H, m, ArH), 7.69 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.71–7.92 (2H, m, ArH), 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, CH=CHCO), 12.87 (1H, s, ArOH). [E]-3-(*o*-Methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (33) : Yield 67%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 96–98° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 75.33; H, 5.47. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1640, 1600, 1560, 1510, 1440, 1340, 1300, 1260 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 364.2 (log ϵ = 4.20), 275.2 (3.59), 242.8 nm (3.92); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.86 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.87 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.94–7.92 (8H, m, ArH), 12.91 (1H, s, ArOH). [E]-3-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (34) : Yield 68%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 137° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 71.87; H, 4.51. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 71.90; H, 4.15%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1590, 1490, 1440, 1250 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 251.6 (log ϵ = 3.91), 373.6 nm (4.03); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 6.06 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.85–7.59 (3H, m, ArH), 7.69–7.90 (4H, m, ArH), 12.88 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 101.67, 106.68, 108.69, 117.96, 118.72, 120.01, 125.67, 129.03, 129.44, 136.15, 145.26, 148.45, 150.24, 163.49, 193.49. [E]-3-(*p*-Fluorophenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (35) : Yield 76%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 75–76° (pet. ether) (lit.^{42a} 77–78°) (Found : C, 74.33; H, 4.01. C₁₅H₁₀O₂F calcd. for : C, 74.68; H, 4.18%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1640, 1580, 1510, 1440, 1350 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 316 (log ϵ = 4.27), 228 nm (3.99); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.95–7.65, 7.68–7.91, 7.93–7.95 (8H, m, ArH), 12.78 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 25.96, 115.17, 115.46, 117.93, 118.89, 118.93, 128.64, 129.61, 129.72, 135.53, 143.19, 162.66. [E]-3-(*m*-Methoxy-*p*-benzyloxyphenyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (36) : Yield 69%, bright yellow solid, m.p. 112–113° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 76.32; H, 5.46. C₂₃H₂₀O₄ calcd. for : C, 76.64; H, 5.59%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660, 1600, 1550, 1520, 1440, 1340, 1300 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 365 (log ϵ = 4.26), 275.8 (3.61), 242.6 nm (3.98); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.97 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.94–7.33, 7.35–7.66, 7.69–7.97 (12H, m, ArH), 12.91 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 56.14, 70.86, 110.88, 113.42, 117.90, 118.76, 120.09, 123.34, 127.21, 127.23, 128.11, 128.68, 128.74, 129.54, 136.21, 136.40, 145.64, 149.81, 150.94, 163.55, 193.59. [E]-3-(2'-Thienyl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

(37) : Yield 72%, yellowish brown-solid, m.p. 91–92° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 68.37; H, 4.43. C₁₃H₁₀O₂S calcd. for : C, 68.09; H, 4.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650, 1580, 1550, 1490, 1370 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 316 (log ϵ = 4.25), 232.6 nm (4.08); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz, CH=CHCO), 7.87 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CHCO), 6.98–7.52, 7.54–7.86, 7.89–7.96 (7H, m, ArH), 12.85 (1H, s, ArOH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 30.06, 118.96, 119.17, 119.22, 120.28, 128.89, 129.88, 129.91, 133.13, 136.72, 138.24, 140.52, 163.90, 193.50.

Flavanones and chromanones 38–49. General procedure : The hydroxy-chalcones 28–37 when refluxed with *p*-TSA in benzene for 6–8 h afforded 38–47. The title compounds could also be obtained by stirring a mixture of the hydroxychalcones, glacial acetic acid and phosphoric acid at 80° for 15 min and then cooled to room temperature, poured over crushed ice, extracted with CHCl₃ (3×75 ml), the combined CHCl₃ layers washed, dried (anh. Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The residue upon column chromatography (silica gel 60–120 mesh) with 1 : 1 CHCl₃-petroleum ether as eluent afforded the products : *Flavanone* (38) : Yield 68%, white solid, m.p. 75–76° (pet. ether) (lit.^{19b,45} 76–78°) (Found : C, 80.30; H, 5.55. C₁₅H₁₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.34; H, 5.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1610, 1580, 1470, 1310, 1240 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 320.4 (log ϵ = 3.54), 252.6 nm (3.92); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.91 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 18, Hz), 3.11 (1H, dd, *J* 12, 17.6 Hz), 5.49 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 12 Hz), 7.05–7.95 (9H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.63, 79.56, 118.08, 120.85, 121.57, 126.09, 126.33, 127.00, 128.74, 138.65, 161.50, 191.99. *4'-Methylflavanone* (39) : Yield 65%, white solid, m.p. 58–60° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 80.74; H, 6.13. C₁₆H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.64; H, 5.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1610, 1580, 1470, 1310, 1230 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 321 (log ϵ = 3.47), 252.4 nm (3.89); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.44 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.88 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 16.8 Hz), 3.11 (1H, dd, *J* 13.2, 16.9 Hz), 5.46 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 13.4 Hz), 7.04–7.96 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 21.65, 44.98, 79.95, 118.57, 121.32, 121.96, 126.63, 129.93, 136.13, 139.16, 162.05, 192.65. *3'-Methylflavanone* (40) : Yield 63%, white solid, m.p. 112–114° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 81.02; H, 5.97. C₁₆H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 80.64; H, 5.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1610, 1580, 1460, 1320, 1230 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 320 (log ϵ = 3.40), 250.8 nm (3.78); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.39 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.83 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 17 Hz), 3.08 (1H, dd, *J* 12, 17 Hz), 5.41 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 12 Hz), 6.98–7.82 (8H, m, ArH). *4'-Methoxyflavanone* (41) : Yield 61%, white solid, m.p. 81–82° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 75.77; H, 5.50. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1610,

1520, 1470, 1300, 1230 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 321.3 (log ϵ = 3.50), 281.8 (3.24), 252.4 nm (3.98); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.86 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 16.5 Hz), 3.11 (1H, dd, *J* 15, 16.5 Hz), 3.83 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.44 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 15 Hz), 6.95–7.95 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.40, 55.31, 79.29, 114.13, 118.08, 120.82, 121.48, 126.97, 127.69, 136.13, 161.57, 192.26. *3'-Methoxyflavanone* (42) : Yield 62%, pale yellow solid, m.p. 110–112° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 75.23; H, 5.37. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1620, 1520, 1470, 1310, 1290 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 320.8 (log ϵ = 3.49), 282.4 (3.12), 253 nm (3.76); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.86 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 16.5 Hz), 3.11 (1H, dd, *J* 12, 16.5 Hz), 3.83 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.43 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 12 Hz), 6.94–7.95 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.87, 55.77, 79.76, 114.62, 118.55, 121.32, 121.94, 127.44, 128.14, 131.17, 136.58, 160.39, 162.05, 192.67. *2'-Methoxyflavanone* (43) : Yield 60%, white solid, m.p. 116° (pet. ether) (Found : C, 75.61; H, 5.56. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1690, 1600, 1500, 1460, 1300, 1260 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 320.0 (log ϵ = 3.41), 279.8 (3.19), 252.3 nm (3.89); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.85 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 18.9 Hz), 3.10 (1H, dd, *J* 13.5, 18.9 Hz), 3.82 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.42 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 13.5 Hz), 6.94–7.94 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.87, 55.77, 79.76, 114.61, 118.55, 121.32, 121.94, 127.44, 128.14, 131.17, 136.57, 160.39, 162.05, 192.67. *3',4'-Methylenedioxyflavanone* (44) : Yield 58%, white solid, m.p. 122° (petroleum ether) (Found : C, 71.96; H, 4.16. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 71.90; H, 4.15%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1690, 1610, 1490, 1470, 1440, 1350, 1310 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 249.6 (log ϵ = 3.95), 289.2 (3.65), 320.4 nm (3.48); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.84 (1H, dd, *J* 2.7, 16.8 Hz), 3.07 (1H, dd, *J* 13.2, 16.8 Hz), 5.39 (1H, dd, *J* 2.7, 13.2 Hz), 6.01 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.84–7.95 (7H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.57, 79.43, 101.29, 106.74, 108.36, 118.05, 126.98, 136.17, 147.93, 148.02, 161.42, 192.01. *4'-Fluoro-flavanone* (45) : Yield 68%, yellow solid, m.p. 104–106° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 74.97; H, 4.13. C₁₅H₁₀O₂ calcd. for : C, 74.68; H, 4.18%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1690, 1600, 1500, 1460, 1360, 1300, 1230 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 321 (log ϵ = 3.52), 252.4 nm (3.86); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.85 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 18 Hz), 3.04 (1H, dd, *J* 12, 18 Hz), 5.45 (1H, dd, *J* 3, 12 Hz), 7.00–7.92 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 44.62, 96.05, 115.53, 115.81, 117.91, 120.85, 121.59, 127.07, 127.78, 127.89, 134.55, 135.94, 161.04, 161.21, 164.33, 190.93. *3'-Methoxy-4'-benzyloxy-flavanone* (46) : Yield 64%, white solid, m.p. 142–144° (carbon tetrachloride) (Found : C, 76.76; H, 5.56. C₂₃H₂₀O₄ calcd. for : C,

76.64; H, 5.59%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1640, 1540, 1500, 1480, 1450, 1320, 1300, 1280 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 318 (log $\epsilon = 3.62$), 282.2 (3.96), 252.3 nm (4.00); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.86 (1H, dd, J 3, 16.7 Hz), 3.26 (1H, dd, J 13.3, 16.7 Hz), 3.97 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 5.41 (1H, dd, J 3, 13.3 Hz), 5.23 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.96–7.95 (12H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 30.94, 44.67, 56.13, 79.70, 108.75, 108.81, 114.38, 114.53, 118.14, 119.59, 120.91, 121.61, 126.34, 127.06, 127.55, 128.63, 130.58, 136.20, 146.16, 146.76, 161.58, 190.90, 192.23. *2-Thienylchromanone* (47): Yield 61%, yellowish viscous liquid (Found: C, 67.67; H, 4.05. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ calcd. for: C, 68.09; H, 4.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1650, 1590, 1550, 1460, 1420, 1300 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 321.2 (log $\epsilon = 3.56$), 252.6 nm (3.78); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ_c 3.09 (1H, dd, J 3, 16.5 Hz), 3.22 (1H, dd, J 12, 16.5 Hz), 5.75 (1H, dd, J 3, 12 Hz), 7.03–7.94 (7H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 30.10, 44.75, 75.51, 118.62, 122.25, 123.44, 126.31, 126.80, 127.28, 127.41, 128.04, 129.86, 136.68, 139.83, 191.62. *2-Isopropylchromanone* (48): Yield 59%, light yellow liquid (Found: C, 75.58; H, 7.37. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 75.76; H, 7.42%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2980, 1690, 1600, 1460, 1300, 1220 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 319.8 (log $\epsilon = 3.49$), 253 nm (3.86); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 1.04–1.17 (6H, m, $2\times\text{CH}_3$), 2.01–2.10 (1H, m, CHMe_2), 2.57–2.73 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.13–4.20 (1H, m, CH), 6.93–7.85 (4H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 18.22, 18.27, 32.53, 40.37, 82.77, 96.51, 118.19, 121.38, 127.32, 136.06, 162.16, 192.71. *2-(Prop-1-enyl)chromanone* (49): Yield 56%, yellow liquid (Found: C, 74.29; H, 5.47. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 74.61; H, 5.51%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1640, 1550, 1480, 1440, 1320, 1290 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 321.2 (log $\epsilon = 3.57$), 249.6 nm (3.91); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 1.78 (3H, d, CH_3), 2.26–2.37 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.06–4.13 (1H, m, CH), 5.74–6.01 (2H, m, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 6.99–7.48 (4H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 17.50, 18.51, 20.80, 63.18, 80.65, 93.71, 116.75, 121.67, 126.44, 129.69, 130.02, 133.94, 134.94, 151.68, 193.50.

Benzo[b]furans 50-62. General procedure: A mixture of 15-26 (0.58 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (10 mg, 0.046 mmol), K_2CO_3 (175 mg, 1.28 mmol) and LiCl (20 mg, 0.47 mmol) in DMF was heated at 80° for 16 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with water and extracted with CHCl_3 (3×50 ml). The combined organic layer was washed with water (3×50 ml), dried (anh. Na_2SO_4), the solvent removed and the residue upon column chromatography (silica gel, 60–120 mesh) afforded the products: *Benzo-furan-2-yl(phenyl) methanol* (50): Yield 68%, solid, m.p. $73-74^\circ$ (pet. ether-benzene) (Found:

C, 80.59; H, 5.31. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 80.34; H, 5.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200, 1595, 1585, 1490 and 1450 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.4 (log $\epsilon = 3.71$), 277.5 (3.72), 249.5 nm (4.28); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.55 (1H, bs, CHOH), 5.95 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.52 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.19–7.56 (9H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 70.64 (CHOH), 103.99 (C-3), 111.28, 121.98, 122.57, 124.28, 126.79, 127.93, 128.34, 128.56, 140.48, 155.02, 158.40 (ArC). *p-Methylphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (51): Yield 63%, solid, m.p. $72-73^\circ$ (pet. ether-benzene) (lit.^{41a}) (Found: C, 80.43; H, 5.87. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 80.65; H, 5.92%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360, 3300, 1610, 1580, 1490, 1460 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.8 (log $\epsilon = 3.66$), 278 (3.67), 249.8 nm (4.21); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.30 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 6.12 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.47 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.16–7.66 (8H, m, ArH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ_c 19.23 (CH_3), 69.98 (CHOH), 104.02 (C-3), 111.29, 121.08, 122.67, 124.34, 126.28, 126.35, 127.89, 128.19, 130.49, 140.21, 155.04, 158.11 (ArC). *m-Methylphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (52): Yield 58%, solid, m.p. 76° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found: C, 81.03; H, 5.96. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 80.65; H, 5.92%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3340, 3300, 1600, 1580, 1480, 1460 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.6 (log $\epsilon = 3.68$), 279.8 (3.61), 250.1 nm (4.26); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.33 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.85 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.04 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.54 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.06–7.59 (8H, m, ArH). *p-Methoxyphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (53): Yield 60%, solid, m.p. $75-76^\circ$ (pet. ether-benzene) (lit.^{41b}) (Found: C, 75.43; H, 5.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2920, 2840, 1490, 1450 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.8 (log $\epsilon = 3.76$), 277.6 (3.81), 251.4 nm (4.23); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 3.36 (1H, bs, CHOH), 3.78 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 5.78 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.46 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.73–7.57 (8H, m, ArH). *m-Methoxyphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (54): Yield 52%, solid, m.p. $79-80^\circ$ (pet. ether-benzene) (Found: C, 75.62; H, 5.37. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2910, 2840, 1480, 1450 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285 (log $\epsilon = 3.75$), 278.2 (3.80), 250.6 nm (4.20); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 3.38 (1H, bs, CHOH), 3.81 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 5.82 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.52 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.79–7.55 (8H, m, ArH). *o-Methoxyphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (55): Yield 62%, solid m.p. $77-78^\circ$ (pet. ether-benzene) (Found: C, 75.29; H, 5.36. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 75.57; H, 5.55%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2920, 2840, 1480, 1450, 1390 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.6 (log $\epsilon = 3.76$), 277.6 (3.80), 251.2 nm (4.21); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 3.36 (1H, bs, CHOH), 3.84 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 5.79 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.54 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.79–7.58 (8H, m, ArH). *3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol* (56): Yield 56%,

solid, m.p. 84–86° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 71.47; H, 4.53. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 71.63; H, 4.51%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 2900, 1600, 1500, 1490, 1450 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285 (log ϵ = 3.86), 278.4 (3.82), 249.4 nm (4.12); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.95 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.85 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.97 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.57 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.81–7.56 (7H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 70.42, 101.12, 103.73, 107.38, 108.16, 111.26, 120.45, 121.08, 124.22, 127.99, 128.30, 134.33, 147.56, 155.01, 158.52. *p*-Fluorophenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol (57) : Yield 61%, solid, m.p. 92–93° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 74.49; H, 4.49. C₁₅H₁₁O₂F calcd. for : C, 74.37; H, 4.57%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 1600, 1580, 1450 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285 (log ϵ = 3.82), 227.7 (3.76), 250 nm (4.16); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.71 (1H, s, CHOH), 5.92 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.49 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.04–7.52 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 30.11, 70.41, 104.47, 111.74, 115.75, 116.04, 121.61, 123.34, 124.86, 128.33, 128.94, 129.05, 136.44, 136.48, 155.49, 158.65, 161.43, 164.70. *m*-Methoxy-*p*-benzyloxyphenyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol (58) : Yield 62%, solid, m.p. 108–109° (pet. ether-benzene) (Found : C, 76.41; H, 5.56. C₂₃H₂₀O₄ calcd. for : C, 76.64; H, 5.59%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 3000, 1590, 1500, 1450 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 305.6 (log ϵ = 3.69), 284.6 (3.83), 277.6 (3.78), 249 nm (4.18); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.68 (1H, s, CHOH), 3.87 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.15 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.86 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.52 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.87–7.44 (12H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 56.03, 70.50, 70.99, 103.88, 110.42, 111.32, 113.66, 115.16, 119.23, 121.12, 122.36, 124.27, 127.22, 127.25, 127.87, 128.02, 128.57, 128.65, 128.82, 130.14, 131.94, 132.08, 133.40, 137.01, 138.33, 148.20, 149.75, 155.06, 158.62. 2-Thienyl(benzofuran-2-yl)methanol (59) : Yield 55%, brown viscous liquid (Found : C, 67.61; H, 4.32. C₁₃H₁₀O₂S calcd. for : C, 67.82; H, 4.37%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360, 1650, 1450, 1400, 1250 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285.2 (log ϵ = 3.71), 278.2 (3.70), 247 nm (4.20); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.69 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.10 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.62 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.92–7.51 (7H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 69.07, 104.40, 111.85, 121.77, 123.39, 124.95, 126.16, 126.36, 127.26, 128.37, 144.33, 155.45, 157.96. 2-(1'-Hydroxyisobutyl)benzofuran (60) : Yield 69%, liquid (Found : C, 75.41; H, 7.34. C₁₂H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.76; H, 7.41%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 2990, 1600, 1460, 1360, 1250 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 285 (log ϵ = 3.68), 278 (3.69), 249 nm (4.16); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 0.89 (6H, dd, 2×CH₃), 1.98–2.33 (1H, m, CHMe₂), 4.33–4.59 (1H, m, CHOH), 6.49 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.02–7.66 (4H, m, ArH). 2-(1'-Hydroxybut-2'-enyl)benzofuran (61) : Yield 53%, liquid, b.p. 76–78°/0.002 mm Hg (lit^{41a})

(Found : C, 76.31; H, 6.27. C₁₂H₁₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 76.56; H, 6.42%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3340, 1600, 1585, 1490 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 284.0 (log ϵ = 3.69), 277.4 (3.67), 249.2 (4.18), 210 nm (4.28); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 1.81 (3H, d, *J* 4 Hz, CH₃), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, CHOH), 5.90–5.95 (2H, m, CH=CH), 6.68 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.24–7.36 (2H, m, ArH), 7.49–7.60 (2H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ_c 17.76, 20.20, 69.89, 80.62, 104.61, 111.87, 121.07, 123.78, 126.64, 128.49, 154.73, 158.30. 2-Hydroxymethylbenzofuran (62) : Yield 58%, liquid (Found : C, 72.62; H, 5.37. C₉H₈O₂ calcd. for : C, 72.95; H, 5.44%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3340, 1450, 1390, 1255 cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 283.3 (log ϵ = 3.52), 277 (3.50), 247.4 (4.10), 210 nm (4.20); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 2.16 (1H, s, CHOH), 4.76 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.68 (1H, s, C-3H), 7.20–7.38 (2H, m, ArH), 7.42–7.58 (2H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from the C.S.I.R., Government of India, is gratefully acknowledged. One of the authors (M.D.) was a C.S.I.R. Senior Research Fellow.

References

1. M. Chen, S. B. Christensen, J. Blom, E. Lemmich, L. Nadelmann, K. Fich, T. G. Theander and A. Kharazmi, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1993, **37**, 2550.
2. S. F. Nielsen, S. B. Christensen, G. Cruciani, A. Kharazmi and T. Liljefors, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 4819.
3. F. Herencia, M. L. Ferrandiz, A. Ubeda, J. N. Dominguez, J. E. Charris, G. M. Lobo and M. J. Alcaraz, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1998, **8**, 1169.
4. (a) C. C. Yit and N. P. Das, *Cancer Lett.*, 1994, **82**, 65; (b) Y. Satomi, *Int. J. Cancer*, 1993, **55**, 506; (c) J. R. Dimmock, N. M. Kandepu, M. Hetherington, J. W. Quaid, U. Pugazhenthii, A. M. Sudom, M. Chamankhah, P. Rose E. Pass, J. M. Allen, S. Halleran, J. Szydowski, B. Mutus, M. Tarcnus, E. K. Manavathu, T. G. Myers, E. DeClercq and J. Balzarini, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 1014.
5. (a) L. W. Wattenbug, J. B. Coccia and A. R. Galhoith, *Cancer Lett.*, 1994, **83**, 165; (b) M. L. Edwards, D. M. Stemmerick and S. P. Sunkara, Eur. Pat. 288794/1998 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **111**, 17706).
6. L. Jurd in "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", ed. T. A. Geissman, Pergamon, New York, 1962, pp. 107-155; (b) D. M. X. Donnelly and M. J. Meegan in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, Pergamon, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 4, pp. 657-712; (c) J. D. Hepworth in Ref. 6(a), Vol. 3, pp. 737-883; (d) E. Middleton and C. Kandaswami in "The Flavonoids Advances in Research Since 1986", ed. J. B. Harborne, Chapman and Hall, London, 1994, pp. 619-652.
7. M. Ito, S. Ishimoto, Y. Nishida, T. Shiramizu and H. Yunoki, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1986, **50**, 1073.

8. N. D. Meyer, A. Haemers, L. Mishra, H. -K. Pandey, I. A. C. Pieters, D. A. V. Berghe and A. J. Vlietinck, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 736.
9. J. A. Beutler, J. H. Cardellina, II, C. Y. Lin, E. Hamel, G. M. Cragg and M. R. Boyd, *Biorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1993, **3**, 581.
10. X. Fu, T. Sevenet, F. Remy, M. Pais, A. H. A. Hadi and L. M. Zeng, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1993, **56**, 1153.
11. J. Parellada and M. Guinea, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1995, **58**, 823 and references cited therein.
12. A. Canstantinon, R. Mehta, C. Runyan, K. Rao, A. Vaughan and R. Moon, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1995, **58**, 217.
13. J. C. Wang, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1985, **54**, 665.
14. B. Talapatra, T. Ray and S. K. Talapatra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1204; K. Cimauga, T. De Bruyne, A. Lasure, B. Van Poel, L. Pieters, D. V. Berghe, A. Vlietinck, R. Kambu and L. Tona, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1995, **58**, 372.
15. T. Akama, Y. Shida, T. Sugaya, H. Ishida, K. Gomi and M. Kasoi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **39**, 3461.
16. H. Kondo, S. Nakajima, N. Yamamoto, A. Okura, F. Satoli, H. Suda, M. Okanishi and N. Tanaka, *J. Antibiot.*, 1990, **43**, 1533.
17. D. M. X. Donnelly, M. J. Meegan in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, Pergamon, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 4, pp. 657-712.
18. P. Cagniant and D. Cagniant *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, 343.
19. (a) R. Matsushima and H. Kageyama, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 743; (b) J. H. Adams, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 3992.
20. K. Maruyama, and K. Tomanaka and A. Nishinaga, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 4145.
21. R. S. Subramanian and K. K. Balasubramanian, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1469.
22. D. Nagarathnam and M. Cushman, *Tetrahedron*, 1991, **47**, 5071.
23. A. K. Mallik, M. M. Saha, U. K. Mallik, S. Goswami, D. R. McPhail and A. T. McPhail, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 130.
24. A. K. S. Silva, D. C. G. A. Pinto and J. A. S. Cavaleiro, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 5899.
25. D. Dauzonne and L. Martinez, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, **36**, 1845.
26. S. Wang, B. D. Gates and J. S. Swenton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 1979.
27. W. T. Brady and Y. F. Giang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 2147.
28. A. Banerji and S. K. Nayak, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 150.
29. G. J. S. Doad, J. A. Barltrop, C. M. Petty and T. C. Owen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 1597.
30. E. Zubia, F. R. Luis, G. M. Massanet and I. G. Collado, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 4239.
31. D. Mal, K. V. S. N. Murty and K. Datta, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 9617.
32. O. Haglund and M. Nilsson, *Synlett.*, 1991, **10**, 723.
33. J. K. Stille, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1986, **25**, 508.
34. B. M. Trost, *Tetrahedron*, 1977, **33**, 2615.
35. (a) R. F. Heck, *Org. React.*, 1982, **27**, 345; (b) R. F. Heck, "Palladium Reagents in Organic Synthesis", Academic, London, 1985.
36. A. de Meijere and F. E. Meyer, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1994, **33**, 2379.
37. J. Tsuji, "Palladium Reagents : Innovations in Organic Synthesis", Wiley, New York, 1995.
38. (a) L. S. Hegedus, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 2415; (b) L. S. Hegedus, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 1113.
39. D. D. Hennings, S. Iwasa and V. H. Rawal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 6379.
40. (a) C. A. Horiuchi and J. Y. Satoli, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Jpn.*, 1984, **57**, 2691; (b) V. N. Kalinin, M. V. Shostakovsky and A. B. Ponomaryov, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 4073.
41. (a) N. G. Kundu, M. Pal, J. S. Mahanty and S. K. Dasgupta, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 41; N. G. Kundu, M. Pal, J. S. Mahanty and M. De, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1997, 2815; (b) N. G. Kundu, J. S. Mahanty, P. Das and B. Das, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1993, **34**, 1625; J. S. Mahanty, M. De, P. Das and N. G. Kundu, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 13397; (c) N. G. Kundu and M. Pal, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1993, 86; N. G. Kundu, M. Pal and B. Nandi, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1998, 561; (d) C. Chowdhury, G. Chaudhuri, S. Guha, A. K. Mukherjee and N. G. Kundu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 1863; (e) M. W. Khan and N. G. Kundu, *Synlett.*, 1997, 1435; (f) G. Chaudhuri, C. Chowdhury and N. G. Kundu, *Synlett.*, 1998, **11**, 1273.
42. (a) T. Jeffery, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1988, 909; (b) *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 2225.
43. (a) E. R. H. Jones and J. T. McCombie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 733; (b) K. N. Campbell, B. K. Campbell and L. T. Eby, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2882.
44. K. H. Meyer and K. Schuster, *Chem. Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 819.
45. A. R. Ibrahim and Y. J. Abul-Hajj, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1990, **53**, 644.